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Assessing Carbon Dioxide Flux and Environmental Drivers in a Tropical Urban Lake of Sri Lanka

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Scientific quantification of carbon fluxes from inland freshwater systems in Sri Lanka is currently lacking, highlighting a significant knowledge gap. This study quantified CO₂ flux from Kandy Lake, an ancient, tropical urban lake (0.18 km² surface area, maximum depth 12.5 m, 75% <4 m depth), considering seasonal and diel variability. Hourly daytime CO₂ fluxes were measured monthly from January to June 2025 using a floating chamber equipped with an NDIR CO₂ sensor (Sensirion-SCD30) integrated into an Arduino system. The chamber was deployed at the same site each month over water deeper than 2 m. A 24-hour continuous flux campaign was conducted in July 2025. Concurrent measurements included water temperature, wind speed, pH, oxidation-reduction potential, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, salinity, atmospheric pressure, dissolved oxygen (DO), photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), chlorophyll-a (Ch a), dissolved organic carbon, alkalinity, nitrate nitrogen (NN), and total phosphorus (TP). The lake remained eutrophic throughout the study period (TP = 0.14±0.09 mg L⁻¹, NN = 4.18 ± 1.18 mg L⁻¹, Ch a = 14.73 ± 9.56 mg L⁻¹). The mean daytime CO₂ flux was 456.82 ± 783.89 μmol m⁻² h⁻¹ and the 24-hour total flux was 9.59×10⁻⁴ kg m⁻². One-way ANOVA indicated no significant seasonal variation in flux (F = 1.99, p = 0.11). Spearman correlation analysis of the diel dataset identified water temperature as significantly related to CO₂ flux (ρ = -0.50, p = 0.007), with higher fluxes occurring at lower temperatures. DO (ρ = -0.31, p = 0.111) and PAR (ρ = -0.23, p = 0.245) exhibited weaker negative associations but weren't significant, while other variables showed no clear influence. In summary, the results suggest that, short-term CO₂ flux dynamics are predominantly governed by diel temperature fluctuations, with photosynthetic processes exerting a secondary influence, and that seasonal variability is minimal under prevailing environmental conditions.

Keywords: CO₂ flux, diel variation, eutrophic, tropical urban lake, water temperature